

**MODELLING OF TIME-LAPSE SEISMIC AND GEOMECHANICAL
ANALYSIS FOR CO₂ SEQUESTRATION MONITORING
IN GUNDIH GAS FIELD**

BACHELOR THESIS

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for Bachelor Degree of Geophysical
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ABSTRAK

PEMODELAN METODE SEISMİK SELANG WAKTU DAN ANALISIS GEOMEKANIKA UNTUK MEMONITOR PENYIMPANAN CO₂ DI LAPANGAN GAS GUNDIH

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Sebagian besar lapangan minyak dan gas bumi melepaskan CO₂ dari hasil produksinya ke atmosfer, sehingga akan berkontribusi pada pemanasan global dan perubahan iklim. Contohnya, Lapangan Gundih yang terletak di Jawa Tengah menghasilkan emisi CO₂ mencapai 800 ton per hari. Oleh sebab itu, diusulkan agar CO₂ tersebut diinjeksikan ke dalam bumi, yaitu ke dalam reservoir karbonat dari Formasi Kujung. Usulan ini dikenal sebagai *Pilot Project Carbon Capture, Utilization and Storage (CCUS)* di lapangan ini. Agar CO₂ yang telah diinjeksikan dipastikan dapat tersimpan dalam jangka waktu yang lama dan aman, diperlukan program *monitoring* yang baik. Dalam studi ini, survei seismik 2D selang waktu dan analisis geomekanika diajukan sebagai metode untuk *monitoring*. Survei seismik paruh waktu diharapkan dapat mendeteksi keberadaan *plume* CO₂ dengan resolusi yang tinggi. Untuk membuktikan keefektifan metode tersebut, dilakukan pemodelan seismik dengan NORSAR® dan pengolahan data seismik dengan perangkat lunak ProMAX. Model bawah permukaan bumi yang digunakan dihasilkan dari studi-studi sebelumnya, yang mencakup studi geologi dan geofisika reservoir serta simulasi reservoir. Sedangkan parameter elastisitas batuan, baik keadaan awal (baseline) maupun pada saat setelah injeksi CO₂, dihasilkan dari studi fisika batuan. Data seismik sintetik dihasilkan dari akuisisi dengan panjang lintasan sebesar 5 km, jumlah sumber gelombang seismik sebanyak 251 buah, penerima sebanyak 501 buah, jarak antara sumber gelombang seismik sebesar 20 m, jarak antara receiver sebesar 10 m, dan geometri *split-spread*. Wavelet sumber gelombang seismik menggunakan frekuensi dominan sebesar 50 Hz, namun faktor atenuasi diabaikan. Hasil dari pemodelan ini dapat mendeteksi keberadaan *plume* CO₂ dengan jelas, baik setelah injeksi dilakukan selama 2 tahun maupun 10 tahun. Inversi impedansi akustik dilakukan terhadap penampang seismik sintetik selang waktu, dan hasilnya dapat menunjukkan bentuk dari *plume* CO₂ dengan tepat. Pada bagian akhir dari penelitian ini, sebuah program berbasis MATLAB® untuk menjalankan respons geomekanika dari batuan reservoir terhadap CO₂ yang diinjeksikan telah berhasil dibuat. Kenaikan volume CO₂ mengakibatkan kenaikan tekanan pori dan menurunnya tegangan efektif batuan reservoir. Hasilnya menunjukkan bahwa injeksi dengan laju 800 ton per hari mengakibatkan kenaikan tekanan pori sebesar 1.2 MPa dalam 10 tahun, namun injeksi tetap aman untuk dilanjutkan sebab titik kritis belum terlampaui.

Kata kunci: CCS, geomekanika, inversi seismik, *monitoring*, pemodelan seismik refleksi selang waktu, *plume* CO₂

ABSTRACT

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Most oil and gas fields around the world releases CO₂ from their production to the atmosphere which causes extensive global warming. In Gundih Field, Central Java, Indonesia, for instance, the CO₂ emission is as high as 800 tons per day while producing gas from the field. Therefore, the CO₂ is proposed to be injected into carbonate reservoir of Kujung Formation in this Field. This proposal is so-called the pilot project of carbon capture, utilization, and storage or CCUS. As means of ensuring that the injection is safe and sustainable for long term, a monitoring activity is required. In this study, a time-lapse 2D seismic survey and geomechanical modeling is proposed for monitoring strategy. The time-lapse seismic survey is expected to detect and locate the CO₂ plume with high resolution. To prove the effectiveness of the method, seismic modeling using NORSAR® and seismic data processing using ProMAX are done in this study. This modelling requires subsurface models provided from the available studies in reservoir geology and geophysics, and reservoir simulation as well. Also, the rock acoustic properties both at baseline and post-injection condition are obtained from rock physics modelling. The modelled seismic survey uses 5 km-long seismic line, 251 shots, 501 receivers, 20 m-long shot spacing, and 10-m long receiver spacing with split-spread acquisition geometry. The modelling uses minimum-phase Ricker wavelet with dominant frequency of 50 Hz, where the attenuation is omitted. As the outcome, the CO₂ plume can be clearly detected during monitoring program of both after 2 years and 10 years. Next, the post-stack acoustic impedance inversion is conducted on the processed seismic data result that exactly shows the geometry of CO₂ plume. At the end of this study, a MATLAB® program is created to run a simple modelling of geomechanical response of the reservoir rock to the injected CO₂. The increasing volume of CO₂ causes pore pressure to build up and decreases the effective stress of the rock. As a result, the CO₂ injection with rate of 800 ton per day increases the pore pressure by 1.2 MPa after 10 years, which is still far below the critical pressure, and therefore the injection is proven to be sustainable for 10 years and ahead.

Keywords: CCS, CO₂ plume, geomechanics, monitoring, seismic inversion, time-lapse seismic

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GUIDELINES OF THE UNDERGRADUATE THESIS

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PREFACE

In the long run, only by God's grace can I accomplish my bachelor thesis. I have constructed this final project entitled Modelling of CO₂ Sequestration in Gundih Gas Field using Time-lapse Seismic Method and Geomechanical Analysis, as the final requirement to obtain bachelor degree in Geophysical Engineering of Bandung Institute of Technology. The following people surely have important roles in the overall process. Without their assistance and motivation, this thesis will never be successfully accomplished.

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In the long run, I fully hope that this study can be an important resource for the subsequent studies. I am open to any comments, suggestions, and discussions that can be mailed to ign.nuwara97@gmail.com.

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Yohanes Nuwara

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CHAPTER I INTRODUCTION

I.1 Background

The impact of climate of change in the twenty-first century has changed how people live and also how the natural environment changes in many countries. As a submitter of 464.18 megatonnes of CO₂ every year (World Bank, 2015), Indonesia now is on the verge of its endeavor to reduce the CO₂ emission by mitigation. Gundih field is a producing gas field located in Cepu Block in Central Java, Indonesia. The field has been operating since December 2013 with major gas production comes from carbonate reservoir in Kujung formation. There are three carbonate build-up structures, one of which is Kedungtuban. Major concern in this gas field is high amount of CO₂ in the produced gas, which reaches 21%, and emission of approximately 800 ton per day or equivalent to 15 MMSCFD. Therefore, CCUS (Carbon Capture, Utilization and Storage) activity is planned to inject the CO₂ into Kedungtuban reservoir located as deep as 3.5 km, in the water leg zone. Besides being utilized to reduce CO₂ emission, the injection has another advantage for Enhanced Gas Recovery (or EGR) purpose. EGR has the ability to push forward the production of gas by extending the production plateau time for longer years and therefore, increasing gas reserve. This approach could also increase the recovery factor of gas production of about 39 BSCF (personal communication with ITB team). In this planned CCUS pilot project, the CO₂ will be injected as much as 150 ton per day or 2.85 MMSCFD for totally 2 years injection (1st scenario for CCS purpose only), and 800 ton per day or 15 MMSCFD for totally 10 years injection (2nd scenario for CCUS purpose).

Major concern in geological CO₂ storage is the likeliness of CO₂ to leak and could trigger seismicity. Therefore, to anticipate these hazards, monitoring program is important. Time-lapse seismic survey is one of geophysical application for monitoring purpose, which is useful to detect the injected CO₂ (or CO₂ plume) in the formation. However, monitoring using 2D seismic survey in Gundih field will be challenging because the injection depth is very deep. Practically, as going deeper the dominant frequency of the seismic data becomes weaker, e.g. until 10 Hz. At this frequency, CO₂ cannot perhaps be resolved. The detectability also depends on the type of reservoir as storage for CO₂, which in this case is a carbonate reservoir. What makes seismic study in carbonate is challenging is the sensitivity of this rock to fluid saturation

which impacts to the issue of whether or not the CO₂ plume is detectable in seismic. In addition, pressure build-up in the reservoir after injection will change the behavior of the rocks and put the rocks in a critically stressed condition.

To deal with the aforementioned challenges, modelling is important to mimic the real time-lapse seismic survey on land, to predict the challenges, and to propose the best way to be able to produce good quality of time-lapse seismic data and to detect the injected CO₂. NORSAR® is a powerful tool to perform seismic modelling that is used in this study. Geomechanical analysis is combined with seismic method to predict reservoir rock behavior during CO₂ injection.

I.2 Motivation

The primary purpose of this research is categorized into 5 parts: (1) to determine the acoustic parameter of subsurface model by conducting rock physic study, both before and after CO₂ injection; (2) to simulate a time-lapse 2D land seismic survey using NORSAR Seismic Modelling software; (3) After the synthetic seismic data is produced, synthetic seismic data processing is carried out using ProMAX software, so that the presence of CO₂ plume in time-lapse seismic data could be identified; (5) to run the acoustic inversion method to the post-stack synthetic seismic data, so that the acoustic parameter of CO₂ plume could be estimated; and (5) geomechanical analysis of reservoir due to increasing volume of injected CO₂ and pressure build-up. The ultimate goal of this study is to determine and prove, whether the proposed monitoring program of time-lapse reflection seismic is implementable to the planned Gundih CCUS Pilot Project.

I.4 Research Methodology

The methodology of this research consists of seven main steps, namely literature study, reservoir characterization, rock physics modelling, seismic modelling, processing and interpretation of synthetic time-lapse seismic data, seismic inversion analysis, and geomechanical modelling. Besides NORSAR Seismic Modelling and ProMAX software, Petrel, and Hampson-Russell are also used in this study. Some codes are written in Python and Matlab.

Figure I.1 Research workflow

I.5 Problem Scopes and Assumptions

The scope of the research focuses on the simulation of time-lapse 2D land seismic survey to monitor CO₂ sequestration in Gundih Field. In this research, the synthetic data is P-to-P reflection events and free of noise. The model is assumed to be isotropic and having no attenuation, or Qp and Qs Equal to zero. The reservoir is assumed to homogeneous, therefore the pressure increase due to CO₂ injection is constant at every point in the reservoir.

I.6 Structure of Thesis

1. Chapter I Introduction

In this chapter, the background of this study, research questions, research objectives, research methodology, problem scopes and assumptions, and structure of the thesis are explained.

2. Chapter II Literature Review

Throughout this chapter, the basic ideas and fundamental theory that construct this study are discussed. Also the data availability, literature study, and geological setting are in discussion.

3. Chapter III Rock Physics Modelling

Throughout this chapter, rock physics modelling to study the seismic property change. The discussion consists the steps of doing rock physics modelling, and the results of the modelling.

4. Chapter IV Seismic Modelling

In this chapter, seismic modelling to model the 2D land seismic survey is discussed. The discussion consists of the steps of doing seismic modelling, analysis of seismic data resolution and quality, and the results of seismic modelling.

5. Chapter V Seismic Inversion

This chapter discusses the steps of doing inversion of synthetic data from seismic modelling and the results of seismic inversion.

6. Chapter VI Geomechanical Modelling

In this chapter, the workflow of the MATLAB® program which I created and result of the modelling is discussed.

7. Chapter VII Conclusions and Suggestions

This chapter consists of final conclusions of the whole thesis related to the research questions and objectives, and also suggestions for further studies in the future.

8. Chapter VIII Suggestions

In this chapter, the author suggests several possibilities of subsequent studies that can enhance this study in the future.

CHAPTER II LITERATURE REVIEW

II.1 Literature Study

Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) or CO₂ sequestration is a technology to reduce the emission of CO₂ in the atmosphere. The earth has the capacity of capturing the CO₂, either it is naturally happened in the earth system or artificially human engineered. There are lots of forms of CCS, among which is the geosequestration or geological CCS. Geosequestration involves the capture the CO₂ in the atmosphere, transporting it and long-term storage of CO₂ in the subsurface. This can be done in depleted oil and gas fields, saline aquifer formation, or abandoned coal bed mines.

Figure II.1 The process of geosequestration (Kaldi et al, 2009)

CO₂ exists in solid, liquid, gas, and supercritical phase that depends on pressure and temperature. CO₂ has critical point of 31.10°C and critical pressure of 72.9 atm. At depth greater than 800 m, CO₂ will be compressed because of increasing pressure and temperature until becomes supercritical phase. The density of supercritical CO₂ (sc-CO₂) at this point is 400 times larger than the density of CO₂ in the air, therefore its volume is much lesser and supercritical CO₂ has the behaviour of gas although its physical appearance is much similar to liquid. Injecting CO₂ in supercritical condition is beneficial.

(a)

(b)

Figure II.2 (a) Phase diagram of CO₂, and (b) Density of CO₂ over depth (Nordahl, 2015)

The increasing volume of CO₂ injected causes reservoir pressure to build up. In depleted fields, the pressure must be maintained below the frac pressure. If the pressure cannot be maintained, the pressure build-up will cause the fractures inside the rock becoming re-activated, will cause the CO₂ to leak through the fractures, and may induce seismicity. Monitoring is important to ensure the safety of CCS activities during operation. Besides that, it is important to monitor how the plume develops and migrates. There are lots of proposed geophysical methods in CCS monitoring, presented in Table II.1 below.

One of the methods presented above is time-lapse 2D seismic survey. Time-lapse seismic survey is a repeated seismic survey conducted over period of time (months or years) with same acquisition parameters. This seismic survey is aimed to study the change of subsurface properties. Based on the Table II.1, the time-lapse seismic survey is a common practice for deep subsurface monitoring and detection of CO₂ plume and has been implemented in some CCS and CCUS projects.

Table II.1 Variety of monitoring methods used in the field (Chadwick, 2008)

			Onshore only	Offshore only	Onshore & Offshore	Primary use	Secondary use	Deep	Shallow	Plume location/ migration	Fine scale processes	Leakage	Quantification
Seismic	Acoustic imaging	3D/4D surface seismic											
		Time lapse 2D surface seismic											
		Multicomponent seismic											
		Boomer / Sparker											
		High resolution acoustic imaging											
	Well based	Microseismic monitoring											
		4D cross-hole seismic											
		4D VSP											
Sonar Bathymetry		Sidescan sonar											
		Multi beam echo sounding											
Gravimetry		Time lapse surface gravimetry											
		Time lapse well gravimetry											
Electric / Electro - magnetic		Surface EM											
		Seabottom EM											
		Cross-hole EM											
		Permanent borehole EM											
		Cross-hole ERT											
		ESP											
Geochemical	Fluids	Down - hole / Springs	Downhole fluid chemistry										
			PH measurements										
			Tracers										
		Gasses	Marine	Seawater chemistry									
	Bubble stream chemistry												
	Atmos- phere		Short closed path (NDIRs & IR)										
			Short open path (IR diode lasers)										
			Long open path (IR diode lasers)										
			Eddy covariance										
			Soil gas	Gas flux									
			Gas concentrations										
	Ecosystems		Ecosystems studies										
	Remote sensing		Airborne hyperspectral imaging										
		Satellite interferometry											
		Airborne EM											
Others		Geophysical logs											
		Pressure / temperature											
		Tiltmeters											

One of the most popular CCS fields worldwide is located in Sleipner field, in Norway. The CO₂ is injected into thin sandstone layer of Utsira formation. Seismic monitoring is successfully done in Sleipner field, where Chadwick et al (2008) analyzed time-lapse seismic data from monitoring of CO₂ injection. Figure II.3 below shows the profound change of amplitude in the seismic data from 1994 to 2002 in Sleipner Field, Norway, due to evolution of CO₂ plume. It also shows the plan view of reflectivity change due to the plume. Seismic inversion is used to extract information about the saturation. It shows an anomaly of velocity in the thin sand layers of Utsira Formation that is saturated with CO₂.

Figure II.3 (a) Time-lapse seismic survey result of monitoring of CO₂ sequestration in Sleipner Field and (b) P-wave section affected by CO₂ plume resulted from seismic data inversion in the Sleipner Field (Chadwick et al, 2008)

Additionally, geomechanical modelling is also a common practice in the monitoring program. Verdon (2012) did a geomechanical modelling of CO₂ injection in the Weyburn CCS Field, Saskatchewan, Canada, which is currently one of world’s largest CO₂-EOR project. The source of injected CO₂ came from coal-fired power plant and separated CO₂ from produced gas field in North Dakota in the United States of America.

II.2 Gundih CCS Field Overview

Gundih field is located in Blora District, Central Java Province, Indonesia. It is well known for its gas production in the North East Java Basin, with other oil and gas fields nearby in Cepu Block, for instance Banyu Urip, Sukowati, and Jambaran - Tiung Biru. The outline of oil and gas fields in Cepu Block is presented in Figure II.4. Gundih field has been producing gas for about 10 years from three carbonate build-up reservoirs, that is known as Kujung formation. The names of these carbonate structures are Kedungtuban (the largest reef), Randublatung, and Kedunglusi (the smallest reef). In Kedungtuban reef, there are five production wells, two of which (called KTB-1 and KTB-3) are located in the northern part, and other three wells (called KTB-2, KTB-4, and KTB-6) are in the south. In Randublatung reef, there are RBT-1, RBT-2, and RBT-3, whereas in Kedunglusi there is only one production well, i.e. KDL-1. Recently, the gas production rate from Gundih area is 70 MMSCFD.

Figure II.4 Oil and gas work fields in East Java Basin

The major concern that arises is that the content of CO₂ in the gas produced are 21% of the composition, reaching an emission as large as 15 MMSCFD or 800 tonnes of CO₂ per day. Therefore, Carbon Capture and Storage or CCS is considered the solution for this problem. Gas production has been carried out in the field since December 2013. The planned CCS Pilot Plant is initiated since 2012, but until now the plant is not started yet. The planned pilot project will capture and transport the CO₂ that comes from the gas production and separated in the Central Processing Plant (CPP) and then will inject it in the supercritical phase into the Kedungtuban carbonate reef as deep as 3500 m. The location of the injection well which is called INJ-2 relative to the other production wells and the Central Processing Plant can be seen in Figure II.5.

Figure II.5 Production and injection wells in Gundih Field

The supercritical CO₂ is planned to be injected with rate of 150 ton per day for 2 years purely for carbon capture and storage. To ensure the safety and sustainability, monitoring activity for the project is made. The monitoring will be done after 2 years of injection. After 2 years, the injected CO₂ will be stored in the reservoir. For the second time, the monitoring is repeated after 10 years of the CO₂ stored in the reservoir.

Figure II.6 Production and injection wells in Gundih Field

Additionally, the CO₂ injection is also planned for Enhanced Gas Recovery (EGR) activity. The expectation of this EGR activity is to increase the productivity of gas production by increasing the production lifetime until reach production plateau and increasing the recovery factor. Therefore, the second scenario is injection of CO₂ with higher rate, 800 ton per day for the overall 10 years. Also, for safety and sustainability concern, monitoring program will be done.

The vicinity of the planned injection well INJ-2 on the surface is located exactly on the well head position of KTB-2. Previously, there has been a 3D seismic acquisition acquired in 2001. The post-stack seismic volume has been interpreted, and top of the Kedungtuban reef is as presented in Figure II.4 below. The black circle shows where the location of perforated tubing and this will be used as the entry point of CO₂ injection into the formation. The supercritical CO₂ will be injected to the bottom of the reef flank.

Figure II.7 Seismic 3D volume acquired in 2001

The top of Kujung formation is shown in the time structure map in Figure II.8. The Kedungtuban reef located in the easternmost side. At depth of 3500 m, the planned injection well INJ-2 will inject the CO₂ into the flank structure of the Kedungtuban reef, as seen in the Figure II.4. The injection point of planned INJ-2 well is depicted as black circle in Figure II.7.

Figure III.8 The map of Top Kujung structure and the trajectory projection of planned INJ-2 wells

III.4 Data Availability

The basic data for this study is well data and seismic data. The well data are obtained from the eight production wells, KTB-1, KTB-2, KTB-3, KTB-4, KTB-6, RBT-1, RBT-3, RBT-3, and KDL-1. Each well has geophysical log information, consists of sonic logs (P-wave sonic and S-wave sonic), density log or RHOB, neutron porosity log or NPHI, resistivity log, and also derived logs such as water saturation or SW, clay volume or VSH, and effective porosity log or PHIE. However, not all wells have all of these data and some missing information occurs at certain interval of the log. Table II.2 summarizes the log data availability in each well.

Table II.2 Well data availability

Well name	GR	Caliper	Density	P-wave	Resistivity	SP	Neutron Porosity	Poisson Ratio	S-wave	Water Saturation
KDL-1	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X
KTB-1	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X	X
KTB-2	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	X
KTB-3	✓	X	✓	✓	X	X	✓	X	X	✓
KTB-4	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	X	✓
KTB-6	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	X	X
RBT-1	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X
RBT-2	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X	X
RBT-3	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓

The seismic data used for this study is 3D seismic volume acquired in 2001. Figure II.15 shows the location of each well relative to the seismic basemap. The result of the acquisition and after processing is post-stack time seismic volume, that is called 2001_cep_u_pstm_gf. The seismic volume has been processed for interpretation that results 3D horizons for top of Ngimbang, Kujung, Platform Interior, and Near MFS Tuban (or Tuban seal). Post-stack acoustic impedance inversion has also been done on the seismic data, and then converted to porosity volume.

Figure II.9 Location of production and injection wells on 3D seismic data of 2001

II.5 Static and Dynamic Models

These studies have been worked by CoE CCS ITB. The porosity volume resulted from the post-stack inversion is transformed into porosity model. Porosity model is part of the static model that is available. Presented in the following Figure II.10 is the three static models, namely effective porosity, clay volume, and water saturation. The white stick in the figure is the injection well INJ-2. The static data confirms that at depth of injection of 3500 m, the porosity from static model is approximately 14% and pretty high amount of clay, in the area of water leg where the brine saturation is 100%.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure II.10 Static model slice of (a) Shale volume, (b) Effective porosity, and (c) Water saturation

Based on the static model, the CO₂ injection is simulated to create the dynamic model or reservoir simulation. There are two series of simulations, the first one is injection with rate

of 150 ton per day and the second one is with rate of 800 ton per day. The injection starts at 2019 and is simulated for more than 10 years. Figure II.11 and Figure II.12 show the reservoir simulation result for 150 ton per day and 800 ton per day injection rate respectively. Based on the result below, the CO₂ is injected in the water leg of Kedungtuban build-up surrounded by 100% brine-saturated zone. The 70% gas-saturated zone is located in the uppermost build-up margin or gas cap zone, existing until Gas-Water Contact (GWC) at 2952 m. The maximum CO₂ saturation achieves 50%, with varying volume in 2 years and 10 years. The simulation assumes ratio of vertical to horizontal permeability (k_v/k_h) inside the reservoir is 0.5.

Figure II.11 Dynamic model result of CO₂-EOR injection rate of 150 ton per day (a) M1 or after 2 years and (b) M2 or after 10 years (Centre of Excellence/CoE CCS ITB, 2019)

Figure II.12 Dynamic model result of CO₂-EOR injection rate of 800 ton per day (a) M1 or after 2 years and (b) M2 or after 10 years (Centre of Excellence/CoE CCS ITB, 2019)

According to the reservoir simulation, the CO₂ injection with rate 15 MMSCFD or 800 ton per day for Enhanced Gas Recovery activity can increase the gas productivity, as can be seen in Figure II.13 below. The red curve is gas production curve without EGR and the green curve is gas production curve with EGR. The plateau time happens when the gas production achieves the highest before depleting. The Centre of Excellence CCS ITB concluded that with EGR, the production plateau time extends for 2 years. Additionally, the EGR could increase the gas reserve until 38.84 BSCF.

Figure II.13 Simulated production profile from reservoir simulation (Centre of Excellence/CoE CCS ITB, 2019)

CHAPTER III ROCK PHYSICS MODELLING

The rock physics modelling done in this study is aimed to study the effect of CO₂ on seismic properties of carbonate reservoir using rock physics modelling. In this chapter, the basic theory of rock physics modelling will be firstly discussed, and then the discussion about the modelling process and results will follow on.

III.1 Basic Theory

Essentially rock physics models treat rocks as a composite material which is composed of two elements, namely the solid phase (mineral frame) and fluid phase (pore fluid). First, the mineral frame or the effective medium is composed of different minerals, such as quartz, clay, and calcite. There are upper and lower bounds for the bulk and shear modulus of this elastic composite, which are defined as follows.

$$K_V = \sum_{i=1}^N f_i K_i, G_V = \sum_{i=1}^N f_i G_i \quad \text{Eq. III.1}$$

$$K_R^{-1} = \sum_{i=1}^N f_i K_i^{-1}, G_R^{-1} = \sum_{i=1}^N f_i G_i^{-1} \quad \text{Eq. III.2}$$

Where K_V and G_V are upper (or Voigt) bound for bulk and shear modulus respectively, K_R and G_R are lower (or Reuss) bound for bulk and shear modulus respectively, N is the number of mineral components, f_i is the volume fraction of the i -th mineral in the solid phase (all f_i sum up to 1), and K_i and G_i are the bulk and shear modulus of the i -th component. The effective bulk and shear modulus of the effective solid are computed as Hill's average of these upper and lower bounds. These Hill's shear and bulk modulus are the mineral shear (G_s) and bulk modulus (K_s).

$$K_H = \frac{K_V + K_R}{2}, G_H = \frac{G_V + G_R}{2} \quad \text{Eq. III.3}$$

Density of the mineral frame as matrix of the rock is calculated using the fraction of minerals in the rock and its individual mineral density (ρ_i), expressed below.

$$\rho_m = \sum_{i=1}^N f_i \rho_i \quad \text{Eq. III.4}$$

Second, the fluid phase (pore fluid) is also composed of individual fluid components, such as brine water, hydrocarbon (oil and gas), and in the case of CO₂ sequestration is the supercritical CO₂. There are many methods of computing individual fluid properties (bulk modulus K_f and density ρ_f), namely Batzle and Wang (1991), Span and Wagner (1998), and FLAG (2014). The widely used method is Batzle and Wang (1991). However, it was found that the method becomes not suitable for fluid at high temperature and high pressure because the method gives lower result than laboratory result, for example fluid at supercritical condition. Span and Wagner (1998) calculated the fluid property by deriving thermodynamics Equation of state. The most recent model, FLAG (Fluid Application of Geophysics), is so far the best method to calculate fluid property at high temperature and pressure. The model was developed by Batzle and Han from Colorado School of Mines, most recently updated in 2014, and applied in CO₂ seismic modelling by many researchers such as Brown (2002) in Weyburn field, Saskatchewan, Canada.

Figure III.1 (a) Bulk modulus of brine, (b) Density of brine, (c) Bulk modulus of CO₂, and (d) Bulk modulus of CO₂ (Brown, 2002)

Similar to matrix component, the fluid is a mixed component of individual fluids. Therefore, the individual fluids are mixed. There are three types of fluid mixing, considering

the patch type in the rock, namely homogeneous or uniform mixing (Reuss), intermediate patchy saturation (Brie), and patchy saturation (Voigt). When the fluids are not uniformly mixed, Reuss averaging will not work. This can happen when porosity is heterogeneous as it is common in carbonates and also during injection and production displacement processes. According to Hampson and Russell (2014), In carbonates, intermediate patchy saturation is enough. The formula for Brie mixing is as follows:

$$K_f = (K_w - K_g)S_w^e + K_g \quad \text{Eq. III.5}$$

Where K_f is fluid bulk modulus, K_w is brine bulk modulus, K_g is gas bulk modulus, S_w is water saturation, and e is Brie exponent (set to be 2).

Figure III.2 Three curve types of fluid saturation mixing for (a) fluid bulk modulus and (b) fluid velocity (Hampson-Russell 10.2)

The saturated density after pore fluid occupies the pore space in the rock is given by this following formula:

$$\rho_b = (1 - \phi)\rho_m + \phi\rho_{fl} \quad \text{Eq. III.6}$$

Where ρ_b is the bulk density or RHOB, ϕ is porosity, ρ_m is matrix density, and ρ_{fl} is fluid density. This ρ_b is also known as ρ_{sat} or saturated density.

Finally, the rock model is complete after the solid component (matrix) and fluid component (pore fluid) are calculated. The pore fluid composition in the matrix affects the seismic velocities (P-wave and S-wave velocity) and density of the rock. There are several

methods used for rock seismic property calculation, two of which are most popular, namely Biot–Gassmann fluid replacement method and Kuster–Toksöz method.

Biot–Gassmann fluid replacement is a method to calculate the seismic property of rocks when pore fluid (commonly oil or gas) replaces the brine saturation inside the rocks. In Biot–Gassmann method, these five assumptions are made (NORSAR, 2014):

- The rock behaves as poroelastic medium.
- The pore and grain sizes are much smaller than the wavelength of the seismic wave.
- The solid grains are all connected.
- The pore space is connected (pore spaces that are isolated are treated as a part of the solid material with lower effective density).
- The medium is fully saturated.

In rock velocities calculation, the saturated bulk modulus is calculated first. The formula for fluid replacement calculation is described as follows:

$$\frac{K_{sat}}{K_s - K_{sat}} = \frac{K_d}{K_s - K_d} = \frac{K_f}{\phi(K_s - K_d)} \quad \text{Eq. III.7}$$

Where K_{sat} is saturated bulk modulus, K_d is dry bulk modulus, K_s is matrix bulk modulus, K_f is fluid bulk modulus, and ϕ is porosity.

The Kuster–Toksöz model (1974) is constructed to calculate the elastic moduli of a two-phase composite medium (effective continuing matrix with inclusions of the other phase) given the properties, concentrations and shapes of the inclusions and the matrix material. The inclusion material could be the pore fluid. For spherical pores, the effective bulk modulus is calculated first.

$$\frac{K^* - K_m}{3K^* + 4G_m} = c \frac{K' - K_m}{3K' + 4G_m} \quad \text{Eq. III.8}$$

Where K^* is effective bulk modulus, K_m is matrix bulk modulus, K' is inclusion bulk modulus, and G_m is matrix shear modulus. Second, the effective shear modulus is calculated.

$$\frac{G^* - G_m}{6G^*(K_m + 2G_m) + G_m(9K_m + 8G_m)} = c \frac{G' - G_m}{6G'(K_m + 2G_m) + G_m(9K_m + 8G_m)} \quad \text{Eq. III.9}$$

Where G^* is effective shear modulus and G' is inclusion shear modulus. Third, the density is calculated.

$$\rho^* - \rho_m = c(\rho' - \rho_m) \quad \text{Eq. III.10}$$

Where ρ^* is effective density, ρ_m is matrix density, ρ' is inclusion density, and c is the inclusion volume concentration (or porosity) which is defined as:

$$c = \frac{1}{R^3} \sum_{j=1}^N r_j^3 \quad \text{Eq. III.11}$$

Where R is radius of spherical pore, r_j is the radiuses of the inclusions, and N is the number of inclusions in the sample. The formula is also modified for different pore shapes, such as spheroid pores with aspect ratio defined.

Figure III.3 Effect of different pore aspect ratios (pore shapes) on carbonate velocity

Biot–Gassmann is most suitable for clastic sediments, such as sandstone or shale, whereas Kuster–Toksöz is suitable for any rock types, including carbonates. Kuster–Toksöz is valid for carbonates because the theory defines that there is no interaction of pores inside the rocks. Likewise, most carbonates have low connectivity of the pores (isolated pores) unlike clastic sediments, such as sandstones, do. This theory also includes the effect of pore shape to the calculation. Also, carbonates have many kinds and shapes of porosity that depends on the sedimentation and dissolution process during the diagenesis of the rock, for example vugs, fractures, and many others.

In terms of the effect of hydrocarbon (oil or gas) saturation on the seismic velocity of carbonate rocks, Li et al (2003) published a paper of their experiment on seismic velocities of carbonates due to effect of gas saturation. In carbonates, fluids have little effect on carbonate rock properties because carbonate rocks have very high modulus. However, V_p , V_s , and V_p/V_s ratio cross-plot are useful to study the effect of gas on the carbonates. The gas effect is discernible in the cross-plot as shown below.

Figure III.4 Gas effect on dolomitic carbonate rock properties (Li et al, 2003)

The final output of this rock physics model is elastic parameter, which is the P-wave velocity (V_p) and S-wave velocity (V_s). Both of these elastic parameters are clearly expressed in the following Equations.

$$V_p = \sqrt{\frac{K_{sat} + \frac{4}{3}G_{sat}}{\rho_{sat}}}, V_s = \sqrt{\frac{K_{sat}}{\rho_{sat}}} \quad \text{Eq. III.12}$$

From these two important seismic properties, other derived properties such as P-impedance, S-impedance, P-to-S-velocity ratio (V_p/V_s), and Poisson's ratio can be derived.

III.2 Rock Physics Modelling Process and Results

The input for modelling is two well data from KTB-1 and KTB-2. The workflow is divided into seven calculation steps.

First, the matrix density is calculated. The input data for calculation is bulk density log (RHOB) which the saturation is 100% brine. From Eq. III.6, the matrix density could be calculated. In the above Figure III.5 of KTB-1 well log data, the water saturation (SW) log

confirms the gas-water contact at 2927 m where 70% gas-saturated changes to 100% brine-saturated. At this condition, ρ_{fl} overall becomes the brine density. The density of brine is calculated using FLAG method introduced by Han et al (2010). For the calculation of fluid density, reservoir temperature, pressure, and salinity are required. The data has been already available in the report of Pertamina (2001). The reservoir temperature at 3500 m is 157.975°C, reservoir pore pressure is 34 MPa, and brine salinity (see Appendix A) is calculated from amount of chloride ion (Cl⁻), which is 11500 ppm. The calculation results brine density of 0.936 g/cc. Matrix density log could be resampled by 10 ms increment. Based on the result, the average matrix density is 2.73 g/cc.

Figure III.5 KTB-1 log data

Second, the mineral composition is determined using Eq. III.4. There are four unknown variables, the fractions of the four minerals. Therefore, a forward calculation technique to find the mineral fractions as such that the calculated ρ_m is close to ρ_m calculated previously from RHOB, is used. The best combination is 40% calcite, 24% clay, 2% quartz, and 34% dolomite. These numbers are in agree with the static model and report. The high amount of dolomite is confirmed in the report by Pertamina (2001) stating that lower reef of Kujung has significant amount of dolomite.

Third, the matrix modulus is directly calculated based on this mineral composition using Voigt-Reuss-Hill (VRH) method in Eq. III.1, III.2, and III.3. The calculation leads to matrix bulk modulus of 58.38 GPa and matrix shear modulus of 24.37 GPa.

Fourth, the elastic properties (P-wave, S-wave velocity, and density) of that 100% brine-saturated rock are computed using Kuster–Toksöz fluid inclusion method. The Kuster–Toksöz method is implemented in Python code script. The code script can be accessed in **Appendix D**. The input for Kuster–Toksöz method is the matrix property (density ρ_m , bulk modulus K_m , and shear modulus G_m), and also the pore fluid (density ρ_f , bulk modulus K_f , and shear modulus G_f) that has been already computed previously. Pore model is also required for Kuster–Toksöz method. The Kuster–Toksöz pore consists of oblate, prolate, and penny-shaped shapes determined by aspect ratios α . Since we do not have an exact pore composition, a pore model is guessed for initial calculation. The program results the calculated V_p . If the calculated V_p does not match with V_p from sonic log (4800 m/s), the pore model must be updated. Then, the calculation is iterated until both V_p values match. It is found that the most optimum model consists of pore with $\alpha = 0.99$ (79% concentration of total porosity) and $\alpha = 0.1$ (21% concentration of total porosity). Using that pore model, the result of 100% brine-saturated P-velocity is 4802 m/s, S-velocity is 2618 m/s, and density is 2.48 g/cc.

Fifth, the elastic properties of dry rock are calculated. For dry rock calculation, K_f and ρ_f equals 0. Using the above pore model, the resulted dry bulk modulus (K_d) is 32.37 GPa. Dry bulk modulus is then used for calculation of pore bulk modulus using Zimmermann (1984) equation given below:

$$\frac{1}{K_d} = \frac{1}{K_s} + \frac{\phi}{K_\phi} \quad \text{Eq. III.14}$$

Using the above Zimmermann relation, the calculated pore bulk modulus is 12.36 GPa. The small pore incompressibility is understandable because the rock type is a carbonate.

Sixth, the increase of pore pressure in the reservoir rock due to injection of supercritical CO₂ is calculated simply using very simple pressure calculator formula known in reservoir engineering, given by as follows:

$$dP = \frac{1}{V_p} \cdot \frac{dV}{\beta_f} \quad \text{Eq. III.15}$$

Where dP is pore pressure change after certain period of time, V_p pore volume of the reservoir, dV injected fluid volume after certain period of time, and β_f pore compressibility or reservoir compressibility. β_f can be directly calculated by taking the inverse of pore compressibility, $8 \times 10^{-11} Pa^{-1}$. The injected CO₂ volume is as much as the constant volume from injection rate. The pore volume is defined as pore fraction or porosity times bulk volume, given as follows:

$$V_p = \phi \times V_b \quad \text{Eq. III.16}$$

The bulk volume has been calculated using Petrel. For rate of 800 ton per day, the pore pressure increase is 0.24 MPa after 2 years and 1.2 MPa after 10 years. For rate of 150 ton per day, the increase of pore pressure is very small, only 0.24 after 2 years and after 10 years.

Finally, the CO₂-saturated elastic properties of the carbonate rock are computed. Two out of nine factors that affect the seismic velocity change are CO₂ saturation and pore pressure, as shown below (NORSAR, 2015). The increase of CO₂ saturation and increase of pore pressure causes the seismic velocity to decrease.

Figure III.6 Factors affecting seismic velocities (NORSAR, 2015)

The cross-plot between P-wave and S-wave velocity presented in Figure III.7 below shows that the distance between the 70% gas-saturated (blue dots) and 100% brine-saturated (red dots) is not far away or having small difference, meaning that gas has little effect on the limestone of Kujung formation.

Figure III.7 Gas effect on the P-wave and S-wave velocity in KTB-2 well

Before the calculation could be performed, the elastic properties of the mixed CO₂ and brine that occupy the rock pore after injection should be calculated. The property of individual pore fluid (brine, gas, and CO₂) is computed for each fluid, using FLAG method. Then, the individual fluids are mixed using Brie average method because the distribution of fluid in carbonate is patchy. Using Hampson-Russell 10.2 fluid property calculation program, the Brie exponent is 2. The calculation result is presented in the following table.

Table III.1 Pore fluid property of CO₂ plume (inclusion material)

Pore fluid	Pore pressure (MPa)	Density (g/cc)	Bulk modulus (GPa)
100% Brine	34	0.9361	2.24
50% CO ₂ + 50% Brine	35.4	0.4692	0.57

70% Gas + 30% Brine	28.7	0.150	0.70
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Then, each of these fluid bulk modulus and density are inputted to the Kuster–Toksöz program. The result of P-velocity, S-velocity, and density is given as follows:

Table III.2 Seismic property of CO₂ plume

Pore fluid	Pore pressure (MPa)	P-velocity (m/s)	S-velocity (m/s)	Density (g/cc)
100% Brine	34	4802	2618	2.48
50% CO ₂ + 50% Brine	35.2	4715	2641	2.42

From the result of calculation, as CO₂ saturation achieves to 50% after the injection, P-velocity decreases by 80 m/s or only 1.8%. As discussed by Li et al (2006), seismic velocity of carbonate performs little sensitivity with fluid saturation. In addition, the S-velocity increases by 23 m/s or 0.87% and density decreases by 2.42%. Figure III.9 below presents the change of P-velocity, S-velocity, and density as a response to various CO₂ saturation.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure III.8 Seismic property response due to CO2 saturations (a) P-velocity, (b) S-velocity, and (c) density

In the gas cap zone, the P-velocity of 70% gas-saturated reservoir is much lower than 100% brine-saturated, 4686 m/s. The density of gas cap is 2.41 g/cc and the S-wave velocity is 2642 m/s.

Having all rock seismic properties computed using rock physics modelling, these properties will then be loaded to the model created in NORSAR for seismic modelling.

CHAPTER IV SEISMIC MODELLING

The type of time-lapse seismic survey modelled is 2D land survey. The objective of seismic modelling is achieved by generating high resolution and good quality of synthetic time-lapse seismic data, which is then processed to post-stack time-lapse seismic section for identifying CO₂ plume. In this chapter, the basic theory of seismic modelling will be firstly discussed, and then the discussion about the modelling process and results will follow on.

IV.1 Basic Theory

Seismic modelling is widely used to study the synthetic seismic data that approaches the real field seismic data. Seismic modelling requires subsurface model, which consists of properties such as velocity and density. After that, seismic modelling will solve for the particle motion displacement or velocity. The basic method to simulate seismic wave propagation is by solving acoustic partial differential equation, defined as follows:

$$\rho \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \sigma_{xx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{xy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{xz}}{\partial z} + f_x \quad \text{Eq. IV.1}$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \sigma_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{yy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{yz}}{\partial z} + f_y \quad \text{Eq. IV.2}$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial v_z}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \sigma_{xz}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{yz}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{zz}}{\partial z} + f_z \quad \text{Eq. IV.3}$$

Where v_x, v_y, v_z are particle motion velocity in x, y, and z directions respectively, $\sigma_{xx}, \sigma_{yy}, \sigma_{zz}$ are normal stresses, $\sigma_{xy}, \sigma_{yz}, \sigma_{xz}$ are shear stresses, and f is the source function. The density is known, and f is the source wavelet in time domain. The stresses at initial point is zero. The particle motion velocity at initial position and time (source) can be determined. And then, the stresses at the next grid in the model $r + \Delta r$ and time $t + \Delta t$ are calculated as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{xx}}{\partial t} = \lambda \left(\frac{\partial v_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_z}{\partial z} \right) + 2\mu \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial x} \quad \text{Eq. IV.4}$$

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{yy}}{\partial t} = \lambda \left(\frac{\partial v_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_z}{\partial z} \right) + 2\mu \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial y} \quad \text{Eq. IV.5}$$

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{zz}}{\partial t} = \lambda \left(\frac{\partial v_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_z}{\partial z} \right) + 2\mu \frac{\partial v_z}{\partial z}$$

Eq. IV.6

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{xy}}{\partial t} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial v_y}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial y} \right)$$

Eq. IV.7

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{xz}}{\partial t} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial v_z}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial z} \right)$$

Eq. IV.8

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{yz}}{\partial t} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial v_z}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial z} \right)$$

Eq. IV.9

Where μ and λ are Lamé's coefficient that can be determined from the velocity and density model. After the stresses are calculated, these stresses are iteratively calculated back to Eq. IV.1, IV.2, and IV.3 to find for the particle motion velocity at grid $r + \Delta r$ and time $t + \Delta t$. Following that, the stresses are again computed for the next grid $r + 2\Delta r$ and time $t + 2\Delta t$. This system of Equation is solved iteratively until all points have particle motion velocity. This system can be solved using finite difference method. The result is wavefield snapshot.

The seismic modelling of NORSAR® Software Suite uses two methods, Wavefront Construction and Ray Shooting. The difference is that Wavefront Construction works with the above principle, whereas Ray Shooting works with ordinary principle of Cerveny (2001).

Seismic wave is signal that propagates in the subsurface layers of the earth. A seismogram is signal (as function of time) representation of seismic wave. It is mathematically resulted from convolution of the reflectivity or amplitude with a wavelet. A wavelet is a pulse that is related to the source and having phase. In seismic survey that uses explosive sources, the wavelet is Ricker with minimum phase. The convolution is expressed as follows.

$$S(t) = A(t) * W(t)$$

Eq. IV.10

Where $S(t)$ is synthetic seismogram, $A(t)$ is amplitude of seismic event, and $W(t)$ is the wavelet. Therefore, after the seismic events are traced, the reflection events are convolved with wavelet so that synthetic seismogram is produced.

The acoustic impedance AI is a product of the density and acoustic velocity (P-wave or S-wave) of the material in the subsurface.

$$AI = \rho \cdot V_p \quad \text{Eq. IV.11}$$

Where AI is the P-impedance, ρ is density, and V is the acoustic velocity. The reflection coefficient is the reflectivity of subsurface layers, either transmitted or reflected. For different incident angle, the reflectivity is different. The reflection coefficient of normal incidence is defined by the following Equation.

$$RC = \frac{AI_2 - AI_1}{AI_2 + AI_1} \quad \text{Eq. IV.12}$$

Where AI_1 is the P-impedance in the upper layer and AI_2 is the P-impedance in the lower layer. The reflection coefficient can both be negative and positive, depends on which layer has higher or lower impedance.

In seismic imaging, resolution is a very important thing. Whether or not the target we want to image is resolved depends on resolution. Bad resolution will make the target not clearly imaged. Vertical seismic resolution is defined as the tuning thickness or resolvable thickness. It is the minimum thickness of a subsurface body so that the reflection of its upper and lower surface interferes. The reflection must not interfere so that the upper and lower surface could be resolved.

$$VR = \frac{1}{4} \lambda \quad \text{Eq. IV.13}$$

Besides resolution, quality is another important consideration in our seismic data that depends on the acquisition design on the surface. Common phenomenon that upsets resolution of seismic data is spatial aliasing. Spatial aliasing commonly occurs in dipping lithologies such as anticlines or carbonate build-ups. Changing the receiver spacing in the acquisition can affect the spatial aliasing in the data. The best group interval is a function of dip angle of the lithology (Vermeer, 2002), given by as follows:

$$GI = 0.5 \times \left(\frac{V_{min}}{F_{max}} \right) \times \sin(\theta) \quad \text{Eq. IV.14}$$

Where V_{min} is the average velocity of the lithology, F_{max} is the frequency, and θ is the dip angle.

IV.2 Seismic Modelling Process and Results

NORSAR® Software Suite is used for seismic modelling. The workflow for seismic modelling is divided into five steps, namely (1) model building, (2) Wavefront Construction ray tracing, (3) acquisition parameter study, (4) processing into post-stack data, and (5) time-lapse interpretation.

First, the initial model is built. We have discussed earlier that there are two cases, injection for CCS with rate of 150 ton/day and injection for CO₂-EOR with rate of 800 ton/day. Each case has three different monitor episodes because there will be three series of time-lapse survey, first in the year 2019 before injection (M0), second in the year 2021 after 2 years of injection (M1), and third in the year 2029 after 10 years of injection (M2). There are three property model, namely the P-velocity, S-velocity, and density model. The input is 3D horizon surface that is available from the static model, namely Ngimbang, Kujung, Platform Interior, and Near MFS Tuban or Tuban seal (from lowermost to top-most). Other top of structure horizons such as Tuban and Ngrayong are picked. Figure IV.1 below is 2.5-dimensional surface of Kujung plus the CO₂ plume.

Figure IV.1 Two-half dimensional (2.5D) model built in NORSAR-3D

The velocities and density properties are included into the 2D model. P-velocity and density values are added into the model by value averaging from sonic and density logs. The property of Kujung has been discussed previously. The model is assumed to be isotropic and no attenuation. See the following Table IV.1. for velocities and density property values of each lithology.

Table IV.1 Property value of the model

Lithology	P-velocity (m/s)	S-velocity (m/s)	Density (g/cc)
Kawengan Group	Increasing linearly	Increasing linearly	Increasing linearly
Ngrayong	2820	1239	2.20
Tuban	2400	921	2.15
Near MFS Tuban	2865	1273	2.25
Platform Interior	3820	1995	2.55
Ngimbang	3320	1617	2.15

The shape of CO₂ plume is referred to the dynamic model. Table IV.1 below summarizes the dimension of the plume.

Table IV.2 Geometry of plume

Plume	Volume (m ³)	Radius (m)	Height (m)
150 ton/day, M1	2.74×10^5	59.8	121.6
150 ton/day, M2	1.37×10^6	53.5	152
800 ton/day, M1	1.46×10^6	54	160
800 ton/day, M2	7.3×10^6	108	200

The velocity and density model are presented in Appendix B.

Second, based on the model already created, the geometry for 2D seismic survey is created. The 2D seismic survey will be in line to the injection point (Crossline 6535). The acquisition geometry is split-spread with parameters shown in Table IV.3 below. The length of seismic cable, number of shots, and shot spacing are made constant, except the source frequency, number of receivers, and receiver spacing. The reason is studying frequency and receiver spacing impact on resolution and quality of seismic data. The two frequencies are 10 Hz and 50 Hz, and the two spacing are 10 m and 40 m.

Table IV.3 Survey acquisition parameter for seismic modelling

Parameter	Value
Position	Crossline 6535 from previous acquisition
Seismic line length	5 km

Number of shots	251
Shot spacing	20 m
Number of receivers	126, 501
Receiver spacing	40 m, 10 m
Source frequency	10 Hz, 50 Hz

The length of seismic line must be more than enough to be able to penetrate until target depth of injection at 3.5 km. Using $l = 1.2 \times d$ (Vermeer, 2002), where l is the length of seismic line and d is the image depth target, seismic cable length of 5 km is more than enough.

Figure IV.2 Seismic survey

Third, the 2D seismic survey is simulated using Wavefront Construction method in NORSAR-3D. The type of seismic wavelet is Ricker with minimum phase, because the survey uses explosive source. Figure IV.3 below shows the parameters used for Wavefront Construction ray tracing. The parameters marked in red squares are the important parameter that are modified, while others remain default.

Figure IV.3 Parameters used for Wavefront Construction modelling in NORSAR-3D

The program shows the ray propagation to each of the reflection surfaces. The events of reflection are showed as spikes or spikeogram, as presented in Figure IV.4 (a). The red spikes (P_r6_P) belongs to reflection events from top of CO₂ plume and the dark green spikes (P_r3_P) belongs to reflection from surface of Ngimbang. Figure IV.4 (b) below shows the ray propagation from the last shot to the top of CO₂.

Figure IV.4 (a) Spikeogram of Shot 126 as last shot, and (b) Rays that reflect on the top of CO₂ plume in NORSAR®

The results of common shot gather are presented in the following figures. The CO₂ effect can be easily detected and located in the difference gather by subtracting the result of 10 years of injection (M2) to the baseline (M0) in the first shot. In the common-shot gather, the reflection of CO₂ appears as new hyperbolic pattern that is showed with black arrow. In the differenced shot gather, the hyperbolas of both CO₂ plume top and bottom are visible. The lower hyperbola shows the amount of amplitude decrease on Ngimbang surface, which is caused by the CO₂ plume.

Figure IV.5 Common shot gather of Shot 126 of baseline or M0

Figure IV.6 Common shot gather of Shot 126 of post-injection after 10 years (M2)

Figure IV.7 Common shot gather of Shot 126 of difference (M2-M0)

Different receiver spacing and source frequency result different resolution and quality of seismic data. The two figures below compare the result of synthetic common-shot gather with the use of different receiver spacing and source frequency. Discussing about the effect of receiver spacing, the common problem that degrades the quality of seismic data is the phenomenon called spatial aliasing. Spatial aliasing happens when the receiver spacing cannot correctly solve for dipping lithologies, which in this case is Kujung reef. Based on the result below, spatial aliasing can be seen when uses 40 m spacing.

Figure IV.8 Comparison of Shot 1 between common-shot survey result using receiver spacing of 40 m (left) and 10 m (right)

Discussing about the effect of source frequency, low vertical resolution happens when using low source frequency. Presented in Figure IV.9 is the comparison of seismic trace using 10 Hz and 50 Hz. 10 Hz produces broader waveform, thus surely resulting lower resolution. The use of 50 Hz makes the resolution much better.

Figure IV.9 Comparison of Shot 1 between common-shot survey result using receiver spacing of 10 Hz (left) and 50 Hz (right)

Fourth, the common-shot gathers of baseline and post-injection resulted from seismic modelling are processed in ProMax software to produce post-stack migrated seismic data. Figure IV.10 represents the processing diagram.

Figure IV.10 Processing workflow

Firstly, the geometry is assigned to the common-shot gather, by creating source, receiver, and pattern file, and then binning. Next, CDP stack is done to the CDP gathers. The stacking process requires velocity information as root-mean-square (RMS) velocity. We have velocity information as interval P-wave velocity model that was created in NORSAR previously. The velocity model in depth domain is exported from NORSAR as SEG-Y file. The interval velocity is then transformed into RMS velocity. The stacking into zero-offset is completed and the result of zero-offset stack is displayed in Figure IV.11 below.

Figure IV.11 Result of zero-offset section before migration (baseline)

Finally, Kirchhoff migration is applied to the zero-offset stacked section. Migration is important to bring the stacked reflectors to the true reflector position by summing all the diffraction energies or amplitudes along diffraction hyperbolas to a single point or line that defines the true reflector. The important parameter is migration aperture, which is the spatial extent of summation path during migration. According to Sun and Bancroft (2001), the migration aperture equals to twice of Fresnel Zone (*FZ*), therefore 1.2 km.

Figure IV.12 Result of zero-offset section after migration (baseline)

The whole processing flow is repeated for the four synthetic monitor seismic data, for both 10 Hz and 50 Hz. After finishing the processing flow and resulting the zero-offset stack after post-stack migration, the results are interpreted. The result of synthetic time-lapse post-stack migrated seismic sections are presented in Appendix B. The image of 50 Hz is clearly better than 10 Hz. In the image of 10 Hz, the waveform is more stretched and wider. From the results presented, the reflection of CO₂ can be identified at CDP between 394 and 449. The top of CO₂ plume is very visible in the time-lapse section as weak reflection amplitude. This happens because of small impedance change caused by 50% CO₂-saturated limestone and 100% CO₂-saturated limestone interface. The small impedance change is caused by small P-wave velocity decrease of only 1.8% and density decrease of 2.42%. The most prominent amplitude as effect of CO₂ plume that we can see is the reflection amplitude at Ngimbang. The reflection amplitude, as the bottom of CO₂ plume, is caused by the interface between the lower Ngimbang shale formation and 50% CO₂-saturated limestone.

Figure IV.13 Evolution of CO₂ plume shape as seen by differenced section for rate of 150 ton per day (a) after 2 years and (b) after 10 years, and for rate 800 ton per day (c) after 2 years and (d) 10 years

The CO₂ can easily be identified using differenced section. Difference seismic section is done by subtracting the post-injection section to the baseline section. The differenced sections can be seen in Appendix B. Using differenced section, the evolution of CO₂ plume could be identified clearly. The result proves that 2D land seismic survey using NORSAR® is capable to distinguish the CO₂ plume through time-lapse modelling with the right acquisition parameter. As resulted from the modelling, the use of high frequency (50 Hz) and narrow receiver spacing (10 m) is suggested to result a high resolution and good quality of seismic data. The CO₂ plume in the carbonate reservoir is identifiable in the seismic section.

CHAPTER V SEISMIC INVERSION

In this study, seismic inversion is done to get the image of CO₂ plume from the synthetic post-stack seismic data. Doing seismic inversion will feature the impedance contrast. In this chapter, the basic theory that underlies seismic inversion will be discussed first, and then followed by the inversion process and results.

V.1 Basic Theory

Seismic inversion is technique to create sub-surface geological model based on the seismic data as input and well data as controls. Seismic acoustic impedance inversion is a backward modelling, that uses the seismic record as the input, then inverted to produce the acoustic impedance (or AI) section. There are several methods of post-stack inversion, namely recursive, model-based, linear programming sparse-spike, maximum likelihood sparse-spike, stochastic, and most recently, full waveform inversion. Each method has its advantages and disadvantages. Recursive is the simplest inversion method which works by deconvolving the seismic data with the wavelet. The disadvantage of recursive method is that the result becomes band-limited because the inversion inverts the seismic trace itself, so the AI trace contains similarly narrow frequency range as the seismic trace.

The model-based method, which is used entirely for this study, is the solution to the recursive method that works by avoiding the direct inversion of the seismic data themselves. Nevertheless, model-based method includes additional workflow as presented in Figure V.1 below. First, the initial model that includes density and velocity information is created and then the blocky version of AI value is computed and averaged from well log data. Second, the AI blocky traces are converted into reflectivity and then convolved with a wavelet to recover the synthetic seismic trace. Third, the synthetic seismic trace is subtracted from the real seismic trace to get the synthetic error. Fourth, the error (or objective function) is minimized or converged by updating the AI model iteratively. Finally, the AI model is chosen when the error is minimum and good solution is achieved.

Figure V.1 Model-based AI inversion workflow (Hampson-Russell, 2016)

Basically, the seismic inversion is based on mathematical inversion theory, as follows:

$$r = (W^T W)^{-1} W^T s \quad \text{Eq. V.1}$$

In the process of model-based inversion, the objective function is calculated and should be minimized. The objective function is defined as follows:

$$J = weight_1 \times (T - W * r) + weight_2 \times (M - H * r) \quad \text{Eq. V.2}$$

Where T is seismic trace, W is wavelet, r is the final reflectivity, M is the impedance model initial guess, and H is integration operator which convolves with the final reflectivity to produce the final impedance. Minimizing the first part ($T - W * r$) or commonly called the “hard constraint” forces solution that models the seismic trace, whereas minimizing the second part ($M - H * r$) or commonly called the “soft constraint” forces solution that models the initial guess by using specified block size. Note that $weight_1 + weight_2 = 1.0$. In constrained model inversion, the $weight_2$ equals to zero.

The important parameters for inversion are maximum impedance change, block size, and pre-whitening factor. The maximum impedance change controls how much the impedance value changes for each iteration (ranging from 0 to 100%). The block size controls how blocky the impedance trace is created to approach the original log. Finally, the pre-whitening factor is used as damping to make the inversion process stable.

V.2 Seismic Inversion Process and Results

The inversion is done using Hampson-Russell software. The workflow for seismic inversion is divided into four steps, namely (1) synthetic well building, (2) synthetic well to synthetic seismic tying, (3) post-stack inversion of synthetic seismic data, and (4) time-lapse interpretation.

First, three synthetic wells are created for post-stack inversion of the synthetic seismic data. Each well constraints different locations that are spread on the western, centre, and eastern part of the reef structure. The synthetic data is made for INJ-2 as synthetic well that constraints the CO₂ saturation in the eastern flank and also for KTB-1 that constraints the gas saturation in the centre of the build-up. There is no well available to constraint in the western flank, therefore a new synthetic well named SIN-1 is created. For reference, see Figure V.2. The marker of top of CO₂ plume for M1 is 3400 m (because M1 plume is smaller), and in M2 is 3338 m. The P-wave sonic and density value for CO₂-saturated zone is obtained from the model.

Figure V.2 Three synthetic wells tied to synthetic post-stack seismic data

Second, initial models for inversion are built by interpolation of the synthetic INJ-2 data. The initial model for post-injection (M1 and M2) use the constant INJ-2 log that includes the property change (P-wave sonic and density value). Therefore, there are three initial models,

each for inversion on baseline, M1, and M2 post-injection seismic data. The P-wave velocity, density, and acoustic impedance initial model can be seen in Appendix C.

Third, pre-inversion analysis is done to experiment with the inversion parameters (impedance change, block size, and pre-whitening factor) that leads to the most optimum result which is highest correlation between inverted and original computed impedance log, lowest root-mean-square error, and lowest synthetic error between synthetic inverted seismic and original seismic data. The method for model-based inversion done is using hard constraints. For every of the parameters are iteratively experimented until the result is optimum. The parameters are: average block size 1 ms, prewhitening factor 1%, number of iteration 20 times, and maximum impedance change 25%. This results correlation of 0.973, RMS Error of 388.7 and synthetic error of 0.248.

Figure V.3 Pre-inversion analysis on baseline synthetic data

Figure V.4 Pre-inversion analysis on M2 post-injection synthetic data

Following the analysis, the model-based inversion is undertaken for the baseline and monitor datasets, all with the same hard constraint parameters.

Fourth, the result of the post-stack inversion is acoustic impedance section for baseline and four post-injection monitor seismic data, as presented in Appendix C. The use of three synthetic wells can constraint the whole part of reef, therefore the impedance result is very smooth. As we can see in Figure V.5 below, the CO₂ plume around the injection well can be easily identified. The CO₂ plume is the warmer or lighter colour that represents lower impedance. This is true because the impedance of CO₂-saturated zone is lower than the brine-saturated zone.

Figure V.5 Zoomed-in image of acoustic impedance of CO₂ plume at (a) baseline, (b) post-injection after 2 years (M1) at rate 150 ton per day, (c) M2 at rate 150 ton per day, (d) M1 at rate 800 ton per day, and (e) M2 at rate 800 ton per day

What is interesting here is that the left-side boundary of the CO₂ plume (last monitor) now becomes visible with the application of seismic inversion. In the ordinary post-stack

section that I showed previously in the previous chapter of seismic modelling, the left-side is barely visible. The reflectivity that is caused by impedance difference between the 100% brine-saturated and 50% CO₂-saturated has broad spectrum. The spectrum becomes tapered after convolved by the wavelet to produce synthetic seismogram. This is the reason why the left-side is barely visible in the ordinary seismic data. However, the inversion successfully recovers the reflectivity spectrum.

In the differencing process, all acoustic impedance value in the background will cancel each other and only appears the acoustic impedance difference caused by the CO₂ plume. The four monitor difference sections can be seen in Appendix C. It is important to notice that these results identify the shape of CO₂ plume pretty clearly. The plume is also localized at CDP between 394 and 449.

Figure V.6 Zoomed-in differenced acoustic impedance of CO₂ plume to baseline at post-injection (a) after 2 years (M1) at rate 150 ton per day, (b) M2 at rate 150 ton per day, (c) M1 at rate 800 ton per day, and (d) M2 at rate 800 ton per day

CHAPTER VI GEOMECHANICAL MODELLING

The presence of CO₂ that occupies the rock pores changes the geomechanical properties of the reservoir rock. One thing that we have already known is that the injection of CO₂ increases the pressure inside the reservoir to build up. The concern is then about whether the reservoir could sustain the pressure increase enough. To study and monitor these changes, geomechanical modelling is proposed. In this chapter, the basic theory about geomechanics is firstly discussed, and then followed by process and results of the modelling.

VI.1 Basic Theory

Figure VI.1 (a) In-situ Mohr-Coulomb diagram and (b) Mohr-Coulomb diagram response of injection (Verdon, 2012)

In the subsurface formations, in-situ stresses and pore pressure are naturally present within the rocks as geomechanical parameters. According to Sayers (2010), the stresses in the rocks are present as causes of tectonic processes, sedimentation, burial history, and many other factors, whereas the pore pressure is caused by the existence of fluids inside and within the rock pores. The stress acting on the rocks is divided into three principal stresses: vertical stress (S_V), maximum horizontal stress (S_{Hmax}), and minimum horizontal stress (S_{Hmin}). The basic Mohr-Coulomb diagram consists of these three principal stresses that constructs the circle.

$$\sigma = \frac{\sigma_i + \sigma_j}{2} + \frac{\sigma_i - \sigma_j}{2} \cos 2\theta_k \quad \text{Eq. VI.1}$$

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma_i - \sigma_j}{2} \sin 2\theta_k \quad \text{Eq. VI.2}$$

Where σ is normal stress, τ is shear stress, ij is 1, 2, or 3. The largest stress will be σ_1 , smaller is σ_2 , and the smallest stress is σ_3 . Failure in rocks is a condition where the stress applied to the rock exceeds the strength of the rock. In Mohr-Coulomb diagram, the criteria or limit that stresses must not exceed in advance that the failure will not happen is called the Mohr-Coulomb envelope. The envelope is the linear relations, that is defined as follows:

$$\sigma_c = C_0 + (\tan \phi) \cdot \sigma_n \quad \text{Eq. VI.3}$$

Where σ_c is the critical shear stress when the rock is about to fail, C_0 is the cohesive strength, that is specific for different rocks, ϕ is the internal frictional angle, and $\tan \phi = \mu$ is the frictional coefficient or the gradient of the linear envelope. The critical stress causes reactivation of pre-existing fractures. At this critical point, the fractures will occur with angle θ .

When a stress is applied to a porous material, part of the stress will be supported by the matrix frame, and another part will be supported by the fluid in the pores. The part of the stress that is supported by the matrix is called effective stress, which is introduced by Terzaghi (1943). It is the effective stress that determines the deformation of the rock frame. The effective stress is denoted by subscript and formulated as follows:

$$\sigma' = \sigma - \beta_w P_p \quad \text{Eq. VI.4}$$

Where β_w is the Biot-Willis parameter assumed to be 1 and P_p is the fluid pressure inside the pore space or called the pore pressure. During injection, the increasing volume of fluid will increase the pore pressure, therefore the change of pore pressure decreases the effective stress. This process is defined as follows:

$$\sigma'_f = \sigma - (P_p + \Delta P_p) = \sigma'_i - \Delta P_p \quad \text{Eq. VI.5}$$

Where i and f denote the initial and final. This pore pressure change will shift the Mohr-Coulomb circle to the left, as seen in Figure II.17 above. The circle approaches the failure envelope of Mohr-Coulomb until at some point, the circle intersects with the envelope. At this point, the rock is in critical state where any further increase of pore pressure will cause the fractures to fail.

Injection of supercritical CO₂ into rock formation is responsible to change of pore pressure and stresses of the impacted rock as a geomechanical response. The injection of supercritical CO₂ with certain rate (CO₂ volume injected over certain period of time, usually in daily basis) will increase the amount of CO₂ volume in the reservoir, then the CO₂ will be stored in the rock pores and volume increases. As a result, the effective stresses are decreasing and shifting the Mohr-Coulomb circles to the left, until it becomes critical. The pore pressure at that condition is called critical pore pressure. The pressure increase must not exceed the critical pore pressure. Critical pore pressure is calculated by the following:

$$P_{cr} = \sigma_{cr} + \frac{(c_0 - \tau_{cr})}{\tan \phi} \quad \text{Eq. V.7}$$

Where P_{cr} is critical pore pressure, σ_{cr} is critical normal stress and τ_{cr} is critical shear stress. Critical normal and shear stress is calculated by using Eq. VI.1 and VI.2, and by substituting critical angle (θ_{cr}) to the Equation.

The relation between pore pressure increase and fluid volume increase is well recognized in reservoir engineering. Hornbach et al (2016) analyses the pore pressure increase due to wastewater injection in Ellenburger Formation, North Texas, United States of America. The pore pressure change is defined in Eq. VI.8 below.

$$dP = \frac{1}{V_f} \frac{dV}{\beta_f} \quad \text{Eq. VI.8}$$

Where dP is the change of fluid pressure in the pores, V_f is the pore volume in the reservoir, dV is the injection volume rate, and β_f is the formation compressibility. Formation compressibility is the relative change in pore volume divided by the change in reservoir pressure that causes the change in pore volume.

VI.2 Process and Results of Geomechanical Modelling

To perform the geomechanical modelling, I built code script in MATLAB®. The workflow of the geomechanical modelling is divided into, namely (1) construction of MATLAB® program, (2) simulation run, and (3) time-lapse interpretation.

The algorithm of the program is divided into four steps, namely reading the injection data and pore pressure calculation, plotting in-situ Mohr-Coulomb diagram, plotting response Mohr-Coulomb diagram, and critical condition prediction. The script can be seen in Appendix D. The injection starts at 1 January 2019 and continues to 1 January 2029.

First, the cumulative volume of injected CO₂ is computed in Excel spreadsheet. Cumulative volume is the final total volume at each date of injection. This is required for calculation of pore pressure in the MATLAB® program later on. Volume is simply calculated as the cumulative tonnage of injection CO₂ divided by the density of supercritical CO₂. Cumulative tonnage is also the final total mass at each date of injection which can be simply calculated by multiplying the rate of injection (150 and 800 ton per day) to the number of days since the start date (1 January 2019). The density of CO₂ is obtained from previous fluid property calculation.

Table VI.1 Cumulative volume calculation sample for rate of injection 800 ton per day

RESULT				INPUT	
Time	Rate (ton/day)	Cum. Tonnage	Cum. Vol (m3)	CO2 density (kg/m3)	0.401
01/01/2019	8.00E+02	800	1809.84702	Injection rate (ton/day)	8.00E+02
02/01/2019	8.00E+02	1600	3619.69404		
03/01/2019	8.00E+02	2400	5429.541061		
04/01/2019	8.00E+02	3200	7239.388081		
05/01/2019	8.00E+02	4000	9049.235101		
06/01/2019	8.00E+02	4800	10859.08212		
07/01/2019	8.00E+02	5600	12668.92914		
08/01/2019	8.00E+02	6400	14478.77616		
09/01/2019	8.00E+02	7200	16288.62318		
10/01/2019	8.00E+02	8000	18098.4702		

This above spreadsheet is inputted to the MATLAB® program. The segment for this step in the program is `%%Read injection data`. The program will read the first column (date of injection) and fourth column (cumulative volume). After that, the program calculates the cumulative pore pressure at each date of injection. As we have already discussed previously, the input for calculation is pore volume and pore compressibility (already known). Pore volume is calculated by multiplying porosity to bulk volume, the bulk volume is $4.8 \times 10^{11} \text{ m}^3$. Note that the input is in the script line that is given by `%input`.

Second, in-situ stresses and pore pressure gradient are inputted to the program. The segment for this step in the program is **%%Before injection (in-situ state)**. This information is obtained from research by Rubianto (2016), that can be seen in Appendix A. In 2019, the pore pressure has already decreased because of gas production since 2016. The pressure drop can be obtained from history-matching result, as presented in Figure VI.2 below. The pressure in 2016 was 280 bar and in 2019 became 240 bar. Therefore, the pressure decrease is 40 bar, that is equivalent to 4 MPa. This value is subtracted from the in-situ pressure in the program. The Mohr-Coulomb failure envelope is also created using values of cohesion strength 5.5 MPa and frictional angle 28° , as input. After all the values are completely inputted, the in-situ Mohr-Coulomb diagram is created.

Figure VI.2 History-matching and simulated pressure profile from 2014 (taken from reservoir simulation by Centre of Excellence CCS ITB, 2019)

Third, the calculated pore pressure is included to the three principal stresses to create the response Mohr-Coulomb diagram. The segment for this step in the program is **%%After Injection**. For this segment, the response Mohr-Coulomb is iteratively plot for each date of injection, so that a movie is created.

Fourth, the program will compute when the injection becomes critical. The segment for this step in the program is **%%Critical Condition**. When the program runs and the movie shows the shifting Mohr-Coulomb circle, the pore pressure will increase until at some point, the pore pressure exceeds the critical pore pressure. When this condition is achieved, the

program will be terminated. After termination, the program shows three information in the display, namely the initial (or in-situ) pore pressure, the critical pore pressure, and the date to stop the injection while critical.

The depth of injection is 3400 m. There are two cases for the simulation, namely rate 150 ton per day and 800 ton per day. The results of simulation using both cases are presented in Figure V.1 and V.2 below.

Figure VI.3 The Mohr-Coulomb result for rate 150 ton per day

Figure VI.4 The Mohr-Coulomb result for rate 800 ton per day

The calculation of the effective three principal stresses and pore pressure at depth 3400 m leads to a value of effective vertical stress (S_V) 70.71 MPa, effective maximum horizontal

stress (S_{Hmax}) of 116.82 MPa, effective minimum horizontal stress (S_{hmin}) of 57.64 MPa, and pore pressure 33.05 MPa. From this result, the values are $S_{Hmax} > S_V > S_{hmin}$ which leads to a strike-slip tendency of faulting.

From the result of in-situ Mohr-Coulomb diagram that describes the geomechanical state of the reservoir rock before the injection, the reservoir rock is safe from critical because the gas production has decreased the pressure by 4 MPa, which means shifting the Mohr-Coulomb to the right by 4 MPa. The distance to critical pore pressure is 5.5 MPa. As observed from the result above, for rate 800 ton per day, the injection is svery safe for 10 years until 1 January 2029. The pore pressure at that date is 1.2 MPa as resulted, which is still 4.3 MPa away from the critical pore pressure. The injection with both rate (150 ton per day and 800 ton per day) is even safe for another 40 years ahead.

CHAPTER VII CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

From this study, several conclusions can be drawn:

1. Based on the result of rock physics modelling done using Kuster–Toksöz method, the increase of CO₂ saturation in the rock up to 50% and increase of pore pressure by 1.2 MPa due to injection decreases the P-wave velocity of the limestone only by 1.8%. The reason for this small change of P-wave velocity is that the saturated bulk modulus with brine is slightly higher than the dry bulk modulus, meaning that the carbonate matrix is stiff. Another effect is the decrease in density of 2.42% and increase in S-wave velocity of 0.87%. This only small change makes the sensitivity of carbonate rock, which in this case is Kujung, to the CO₂ is lower than that of sandstone.
2. Time lapse two-dimensional (2D) land seismic survey is applicable for monitoring of CO₂ in the Kujung carbonate reservoir. The time-lapse seismic data resulted from seismic modelling clearly show the CO₂ plume with good resolution if uses 50 Hz frequency for the source and anti-spatial aliasing if uses 10 m spacing for receiver. The CO₂ plume can be clearly identified by comparing zero-offset seismic stack after Kirchhoff time migration of different monitoring time. The use of seismic inversion is also effective to feature the change due to CO₂ injection based on its impedance contrast.
3. The injection with rate 800 ton per day increases pore pressure by 1.2 MPa for 10 years. The reservoir rock becomes critical if pore pressure increases by 1.6 MPa, assuming that the cohesion strength is as measured, 5.5 MPa. Therefore, the injection is safe for 10 years.

In the author's opinion, this study has successfully demonstrated that 2D land time-lapse seismic survey works to monitor the upcoming CO₂ injection in carbonate reservoir of Gundih field. Geomechanical modelling is also useful for evaluation of continuity of the injection in terms of reservoir integrity to store CO₂ and not to induce seismicity. In addition to this study, the author provides several suggestions as follows for anyone who is interested to continue and develop this study even more.

1. The post-stack section results still contain artefacts that are visible in the differenced AI section. The author suggests pre-stack inversion on NMO-corrected CDP offset or angle gather to be added. In pre-stack inversion, Amplitude-versus-offset (AVO) analysis can be done to identify the AVO type of the carbonate rock and the CO₂ saturation. Simultaneous inversion may reduce the artefacts. Also, Lambda-Mu-Rho (LMR) and Extended Elastic Impedance (EEI) are also useful to image the CO₂ based on variety of elastic parameters.
2. The use of reservoir fluid simulator such as FLAC and TOUGH is also recommended. The pressure that the author calculates in this study is using very simple pressure-volume Equation that is basic in reservoir engineering. These reservoir fluid simulators apply the effect of mechanic-hydraulic coupling that happens in every reservoir. TOUGH also has a module that applies CO₂-water-calcite chemical reaction that will make the simulation much more realistic.
3. The author does not have access to review the core from Gundih field and the laboratory tests. The access to laboratory tests will provide a comparison to the author's works on modelling, so that the laboratory test will verify and calibrate the modelling results.

That is all from the author.

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Appendix A Reservoir Data

Table A.1 Reservoir initial condition by Pertamina (2000)

Reservoir	Datum depth (mss)	Reservoir initial pressure (psi)	Reservoir initial temperature (°F)
Kujung Fm. (Carbonate)	3033	4335	320

Table A.2 In-situ stresses and pore pressure result in KTB-1 by Rubianto (2016)

KTB-1	Hydrostatic		Overpressure	
	Psi/ft	Bar/km	Psi/ft	Bar/km
S _V	0.92	208.1095	0.92	208.1095
S _{hmin}	0.75	169.6545	0.77	174.1786
S _{Hmax}	1.52	343.8331	1.25	282.7575
Pp	0.43	97.26858	0.54	122.1512

Table A.3 Brine salinity data (ppm of Cl⁻) data from Drill Stem Test result in KTB by Pertamina (2000)

LU hour	JEP inch	Q Fluid m3/h	Q Gas mmsefd	KA %	Q Oil m3/h	Pressure (psi)			Temp. °F	SG Fluid /60° F	SG Gas /28°C	° API /60° F	PH	Cl ppm	H2S ppm
						TKT	TFL	T SEP							
2907 – 2915 m MD															
1	3/4	10.930	0.247	100	10.930	350	60.0	60.0	110	1.032	0.6250	42	7.5	22000	3000
4	1/4	-	2.621	-	-	1700	56.9	-	105	-	0.6250	-	-	-	1800
4	3/8	-	4.561	-	-	1125	92.5	-	109	-	0.6250	-	-	-	4200
4	1/2	120	5.358	100	1.017	700	156.5	150.0	110	1.017	0.6250	42	7	12600	4700
4	5/8	-	3.422	-	-	640	120.9	110.2	112	-	0.6250	-	-	-	5000
10	1/2	60.0	5.349	100	1.003	800	120.9	106.7	118	1.003	0.6250	42	6.5	4000	5000
2992 – 3000 m MD															
6	1/4	66.980	0.5756	100	-	700	50	42.7	42	-	0.9229	-	7.5	10011	7500
6	3/8	118.090	0.9774	100	-	1200	70	64.0	40	-	0.9553	-	7.5	10800	7500
6	1/2	143.000	1.184	100	-	900	90	85.3	46	-	0.9666	-	7.5	9410	7500
6	5/8	156.15	15.000	100	-	750	40	35.6	50	-	0.9548	-	7.5	9400	10000
10	1/2	134.7	14.358	100	-	1000	43	35.6	50	-	0.9551	-	7.5	9400	7500

Table A.4 Gas specific gravity data from Gas Sampling Analysis result in KTB-1 by Pertamina (2000)

Composition	% Mole
Oxygen (O ₂)	0
Nitrogen (N ₂)	0.30
Carbon dioxide (CO ₂)	24.86
Methane (C1)	69.25
Ethane (C2)	3.14
Propane (C3)	1.54
Isobutane (i-C4)	0.39
Normal Butane (n-C4)	0.31
Isopentane (i- C5)	0.10
Normal Pentane (n-C5)	0.08
Hexane Plus (C6+)	0.03
Total	100.00
Specific Gravity	0.8403
Compressibility (Z-factor)	0.99681

Table A.5 Density and modulus of minerals

Mineral	Density (g/cc)	Bulk modulus (GPa)	Shear modulus (GPa)
Calcite	2.71	76.8	32
Clay	2.58	20.9	6.9
Quartz	2.65	36.6	45
Dolomite	2.87	94.9	45

3087-3089 m

3079-3081 m

3075-3077 m

3055-3057 m

3047-3049 m

3019-3021 m

Figure A.1 Thin slice of petrography analysis in KTB-1 from Pertamina (2000)

Appendix B Seismic Modelling

Figure B.1 P-wave velocity model of baseline (M0)

Figure B.2 S-wave velocity model of baseline (M0)

Figure B.3 Density model of baseline (M0)

Figure B.4 P-wave velocity model of post-injection after 2 years with injection rate 800 ton per day (M1)

Figure B.5 S-wave velocity model of post-injection after 2 years with injection rate 800 ton per day (M1)

Figure B.6 Density model of post-injection after 2 years with injection rate 800 ton per day (M1)

Figure B.7 P-wave velocity model of post-injection after 10 years with injection rate 800 ton per day (M2)

Figure B.8 S-wave velocity model of post-injection after 10 years with injection rate 800 ton per day (M2)

Figure B.9 Density model of post-injection after 10 years with injection rate 800 ton per day (M2)

Figure B.10 Synthetic seismic shot gather of baseline (M0): Shot 1

Figure B.11 Synthetic seismic shot gather of post-injection after 2 years with rate 800 ton per day (M2): Shot 1

Figure B.12 Synthetic seismic shot gather of baseline (M0): Shot 126

Figure B.13 Synthetic seismic shot gather of post-injection after 2 years with rate 800 ton per day (M2): Shot 126

Figure B.17 Synthetic post-stack time section of rate 150 ton per day after 10 years (M2) with 10 Hz frequency

Figure B.18 Synthetic post-stack time section of rate 150 ton per day after 10 years (M2) with 50 Hz frequency

Figure B.23 Differenced seismic section between post-injection after 2 years (M1) at rate 150 ton per day to baseline (50 Hz frequency)

Figure B.24 Differenced seismic section between post-injection after 10 years (M2) at rate 150 ton per day to baseline (50 Hz frequency)

Figure B.25 Differenced seismic section between post-injection after 2 years (M1) at rate 800 ton per day to baseline (50 Hz frequency)

Figure B.26 Differenced seismic section between post-injection after 10 years (M2) at rate 800 ton per day to baseline (50 Hz frequency)

Appendix C Seismic Inversion

Figure C.1 Well-to-seismic tie of synthetic well INJ-2

Figure C.2 Well-to-seismic tie of synthetic well KTB-1

Figure C.3 Well-to-seismic tie of synthetic well SIN-1

Figure C.5 Initial model of P-wave velocity at Crossline 6535 for post-stack inversion of synthetic seismic data

Figure C.6 Initial model of density at Crossline 6535 for post-stack inversion of synthetic seismic data

Figure C.7 Initial model of acoustic impedance at Crossline 6535 for post-stack inversion of synthetic seismic data

Figure C.8 Post-stack acoustic impedance section result of inversion on baseline seismic data

Figure C.9 Post-stack acoustic impedance section result of inversion on post-injection after 2 years (M1) with injection rate 150 ton per day seismic data

Figure C.10 Post-stack acoustic impedance section result of inversion on post-injection after 10 years (M2) with injection rate 150 ton per day seismic data

Figure C.11 Post-stack acoustic impedance section result of inversion on post-injection after 2 years (M1) with injection rate 800 ton per day seismic data

Figure C.12 Post-stack acoustic impedance section result of inversion on post-injection after 10 years (M2) with injection rate 800 ton per day seismic data

Figure C.13 Differenced acoustic impedance section between post-injection after 2 years with injection rate 150 ton per day (M2) to baseline

Figure C.14 Differenced acoustic impedance section between post-injection after 10 years with injection rate 150 ton per day (M2) to baseline

Figure C.15 Differenced acoustic impedance section between post-injection after 2 years with injection rate 800 ton per day (M1) to baseline

Figure C.16 Differenced acoustic impedance section between post-injection after 10 years with injection rate 800 ton per day (M2) to baseline

Appendix D Python Script for Kuster–Toksöz Fluid Inclusion Modelling

```
import numpy as np

"""
Fluid Inclusion Modelling with Kuster-Toksoz Method (simplification of Wang, 1997)
By: Yohanes Nuwara
"""

#Matrix properties
Km = 58.38
Gm = 24.37
rho_m = 2.73

#Fluid properties
Kf = np.array([2.24, 0.5684, 0]) #1st 100% water, 2nd row with CO2, 3rd row dry
Gf = 0
rho_f = np.array([0.9365, 0.4692, 0])

A = Gf / Gm - 1.0
B = (Kf / Km - Gf / Gm) / 3.0
R = Gm / (Km + (4.0 / 3.0) * Gm)
Fm = (Gm / 6.0) * (9.0 * Km + 8.0 * Gm) / (Km + 2.0 * Gm) #zeta

#pore structure
totalporo = 0.14
alpha1 = 0.99
alpha2 = 0.1
compos1 = 0.79 #composition of pore 1 relative to total porosity
compos2 = 0.21
ci_1 = compos1*totalporo #volume fraction of pore 1
ci_2 = compos2*totalporo

#pore 1
theta1 = alpha1 * (np.arccos(alpha1) - alpha1 * np.sqrt(1.0 - alpha1 * alpha1)) / (1.0 -
alpha1 * alpha1) ** (3.0 / 2.0)
f1 = alpha1 * alpha1 * (3.0 * theta1 - 2.0) / (1.0 - alpha1 * alpha1)

F1_1 = 1.0 + A * (1.5 * (f1 + theta1) - R * (1.5 * f1 + 2.5 * theta1 - 4.0 / 3.0))
F2_1 = 1.0 + A * (1.0 + 1.5 * (f1 + theta1) - R * (1.5 * f1 + 2.5 * theta1)) + B * (3.0 -
4.0 * R) + A * (A + 3.0 * B) * (
1.5 - 2.0 * R) * (f1 + theta1 - R * (f1 - theta1 + 2.0 * theta1 * theta1))
F3_1 = 1.0 + A * (1.0 - f1 - 1.5 * theta1 + R * (f1 + theta1))
F4_1 = 1.0 + (A / 4.0) * (f1 + 3.0 * theta1 - R * (f1 - theta1))
F5_1 = A * (-f1 + R * (f1 + theta1 - 4.0 / 3.0)) + B * theta1 * (3.0 - 4.0 * R)
F6_1 = 1.0 + A * (1.0 + f1 - R * (f1 + theta1)) + B * (1.0 - theta1) * (3.0 - 4.0 * R)
F7_1 = 2.0 + (A / 4.0) * (3.0 * f1 + 9.0 * theta1 - R * (3.0 * f1 + 5.0 * theta1)) + B *
theta1 * (3.0 - 4.0 * R)
F8_1 = A * (1.0 - 2.0 * R + (f1 / 2.0) * (R - 1.0) + (theta1 / 2.0) * (5.0 * R - 3.0)) + B
* (1.0 - theta1) * (
3.0 - 4.0 * R)
F9_1 = A * ((R - 1.0) * f1 - R * theta1) + B * theta1 * (3.0 - 4.0 * R)

P_1 = 3.0 * F1_1 / F2_1
Q_1 = 2.0 / F3_1 + 1.0 / F4_1 + (F4_1 * F5_1 + F6_1 * F7_1 - F8_1 * F9_1) / (F2_1 * F4_1)

#pore 2
theta2 = alpha2 * (np.arccos(alpha2) - alpha2 * np.sqrt(1.0 - alpha2 * alpha2)) / (1.0 -
alpha2 * alpha2) ** (3.0 / 2.0)
f2 = alpha2 * alpha2 * (3.0 * theta2 - 2.0) / (1.0 - alpha2 * alpha2)

F1_2 = 1.0 + A * (1.5 * (f2 + theta2) - R * (1.5 * f2 + 2.5 * theta2 - 4.0 / 3.0))
F2_2 = 1.0 + A * (1.0 + 1.5 * (f2 + theta2) - R * (1.5 * f2 + 2.5 * theta2)) + B * (3.0 -
4.0 * R) + A * (A + 3.0 * B) * (
1.5 - 2.0 * R) * (f2 + theta2 - R * (f2 - theta2 + 2.0 * theta2 * theta2))
```

```

F3_2 = 1.0 + A * (1.0 - f2 - 1.5 * theta2 + R * (f2 + theta2))
F4_2 = 1.0 + (A / 4.0) * (f2 + 3.0 * theta2 - R * (f2 - theta2))
F5_2 = A * (-f2 + R * (f2 + theta2 - 4.0 / 3.0)) + B * theta2 * (3.0 - 4.0 * R)
F6_2 = 1.0 + A * (1.0 + f2 - R * (f2 + theta2)) + B * (1.0 - theta2) * (3.0 - 4.0 * R)
F7_2 = 2.0 + (A / 4.0) * (3.0 * f2 + 9.0 * theta2 - R * (3.0 * f2 + 5.0 * theta2)) + B *
theta2 * (3.0 - 4.0 * R)
F8_2 = A * (1.0 - 2.0 * R + (f2 / 2.0) * (R - 1.0) + (theta2 / 2.0) * (5.0 * R - 3.0)) + B
* (1.0 - theta2) * (
    3.0 - 4.0 * R)
F9_2 = A * ((R - 1.0) * f2 - R * theta2) + B * theta2 * (3.0 - 4.0 * R)

P_2 = 3.0 * F1_2 / F2_2
Q_2 = 2.0 / F3_2 + 1.0 / F4_2 + (F4_2 * F5_2 + F6_2 * F7_2 - F8_2 * F9_2) / (F2_2 * F4_2)

sigma_P = (ci_1*P_1)+(ci_2*P_2)
sigma_Q = (ci_1*Q_1)+(ci_2*Q_2)

#1st 100% water, 2nd row with CO2, 3rd row dry
K_sat = ((3 * Km * (3 * Km + 4 * Gm)) + (4 * Gm * (Kf - Km) * sigma_P)) / ((3 * (3 * Km + 4
* Gm)) - \
    (3 * (Kf - Km) * sigma_P))
G_sat = ((25 * (Gm**2) * (3 * Km + 4 * Gm)) - ((Gm**2) * (9 * Km + 8 * Gm) * sigma_Q)) /
((25 * Gm * (3 * Km + 4 * Gm)) \
    + (6 * Gm * (Km + 2 * Gm) * sigma_Q))
rho_sat = (rhom*(1-0.14))+(rhof*0.14)
Vp_sat = np.sqrt((K_sat + 4/3*G_sat) / rho_sat)
Vs_sat = np.sqrt(G_sat / rho_sat)

```

Appendix E MATLAB Script for Geomechanical Modelling

```
%%CO2 Injection Monitoring Mohr-Coulomb Plotter
%%Yohanes Nuwara (12315059)
%%Institut Teknologi Bandung

clear,clc;

%%Read injection data
data_injeksi=struct('date',[],'cumvol',[],'pp_injected',[]);
fid=fopen('InjectionData_800tpd.dat','r');
i=0;
porosity=0.14; %input porosity
bulkvol=4.8*10^11; %input reservoir bulk volume
porevol=porosity*bulkvol;
compressibility=8.0906*10^-11; %input pore compressibility
while ~feof(fid)

    i=i+1;
    str=fscanf(fid,'%s',1);
    data_injeksi.date(i)=datenum(str,'dd/mm/yyyy');
    data_injeksi.cumvol(i)=fscanf(fid,'%f',1);
    data_injeksi.pp_injected(i)=(1/porevol)*(data_injeksi.cumvol(i)/compressibility)/10^6;
end

ndata=i;

fclose(fid);

%% Before Injection (in-situ state)

%input Sv, SH max, Sh min, pore pressure

%Sv hydrostatic=0.92 Psi/ft, Sv overpressure=0.92 Psi/ft
%SHmax hydrostatic=1.52 Psi/ft, SHmax overpressure=1.25 Psi/ft
%Shmin hydrostatic=0.75 Psi/ft, Shmin overpressure=0.77 Psi/ft
%Pp hydrostatic=0.43 Psi/ft, Pp overpressure=0.54 Psi/ft

input_depth='What is the depth of CO2 injection reservoir (in metre)? ';
depth=input(input_depth); %injection depth range=2784 to 2874 m
Sv=0.92*3.28084*0.00689*depth; %input in Psi, converted to MPa
SHmax=1.52*3.28084*0.00689*depth; %input in Psi, converted to MPa
Shmin=0.75*3.28084*0.00689*depth; %input in Psi, converted to MPa
pore_pressure=0.43*3.28084*0.00689*depth; %input in Psi, converted to MPa

%convert to S1,S2,S3
sigma_matrix=[Sv SHmax Shmin];
ordered_sigma=sort(sigma_matrix,'descend');
sigma_1=ordered_sigma(1); %sigma 1 is the largest principal stress
sigma_2=ordered_sigma(2);
sigma_3=ordered_sigma(3);

tau_1 =(sigma_1-sigma_3)/2;
tau_2 =(sigma_1-sigma_2)/2;
tau_3 =(sigma_2-sigma_3)/2;

%%Mohr-Coulomb envelope
friction_angle=28; %input friction angle
c_zero=6.7; %input cohesive strength
sigma_normal=0:1:sigma_1;
coeff_friction_angle=tand(friction_angle);
sigma_shear=c_zero+(coeff_friction_angle*(sigma_normal));

%%Plotting the 3-D Mohr's Circle
```

```

angles=0:0.01:2*pi;

for i=1:30:ndata %time increment 30 days

Centre1=[(((sigma_1+sigma_3)/2)-pore_pressure) 0];
Centre2=[(((sigma_1+sigma_2)/2)-pore_pressure) 0];
Centre3=[(((sigma_2+sigma_3)/2)-pore_pressure) 0];
cirlce1=[Centre1(1)+tau_1*cos(angles') Centre1(2)+tau_1*sin(angles')];
cirlce2=[Centre2(1)+tau_2*cos(angles') Centre2(2)+tau_2*sin(angles')];
cirlce3=[Centre3(1)+tau_3*cos(angles') Centre3(2)+tau_3*sin(angles')];

subplot(1,2,1)

plot(sigma_shear,'r');
axis([0 80 -40 40]);
hold on
plot(cirlce1(:,1),cirlce1(:,2),'b',cirlce2(:,1),cirlce2(:,2),'g',...
      cirlce3(:,1),cirlce3(:,2),'r'),axis Equal;grid on;
title('Mohr-Coulomb before injection')

%Display annotation
if sigma_1>0
    text((sigma_1-pore_pressure)*1.01,0,'\sigma\prime_1','fontsize',15);
else
    text((sigma_1-pore_pressure)*0.95,0,'\sigma\prime_1','fontsize',15)
end
if sigma_2>0
    text((sigma_2-pore_pressure)*1.1,0,'\sigma\prime_2','fontsize',15)
else
    text((sigma_2-pore_pressure)*0.99,0,'\sigma\prime_2','fontsize',15)
end
if sigma_3>0
    text((sigma_3-pore_pressure)*1.1,0,'\sigma\prime_3','fontsize',15);
else
    text((sigma_3-pore_pressure)*0.99,0,'\sigma\prime_3','fontsize',15);
end
text(Centre1(1),tau_1*0.9,'\tau_1','fontsize',15);
text(Centre2(1),tau_2*0.9,'\tau_2','fontsize',15);
text(Centre3(1),tau_3*0.9,'\tau_3','fontsize',15);
xlabel('Effective Normal Stress, \sigma\prime','fontsize',15);
ylabel('Shear Stress, \tau','fontsize',15)

%% After injection

%pore pressure increase
pore_pressure_new=pore_pressure+data_injeksi.pp_injected(i);

%Mohr-Coulomb envelope
sigma_shear=c_zero+(coeff_friction_angle*(sigma_normal));

%Plotting the 3-D Mohr's Circle after injection
angles=0:0.01:2*pi;
Centre1_new=[(((sigma_1+sigma_3)/2)-pore_pressure_new) 0];
Centre2_new=[(((sigma_1+sigma_2)/2)-pore_pressure_new) 0];
Centre3_new=[(((sigma_2+sigma_3)/2)-pore_pressure_new) 0];
cirlce1_new=[Centre1_new(1)+tau_1*cos(angles') Centre1_new(2)+tau_1*sin(angles')];
cirlce2_new=[Centre2_new(1)+tau_2*cos(angles') Centre2_new(2)+tau_2*sin(angles')];
cirlce3_new=[Centre3_new(1)+tau_3*cos(angles') Centre3_new(2)+tau_3*sin(angles')];

subplot(1,2,2)
plot(sigma_shear,'b');
axis([0 80 -40 40]);
hold on
plot(cirlce1_new(:,1),cirlce1_new(:,2),'b',cirlce2_new(:,1),cirlce2_new(:,2),'g',...
      cirlce3_new(:,1),cirlce3_new(:,2),'r'),axis Equal;grid on;
hold off

```

```

title('Mohr-Coulomb after injection')

%Display annotation
if sigma_1>0
    text((sigma_1-pore_pressure_new)*1.01,0,'\sigma\prime_1','fontsize',15);
else
    text((sigma_1-pore_pressure_new)*0.95,0,'\sigma\prime_1','fontsize',15)
end
if sigma_2>0
    text((sigma_2-pore_pressure_new)*1.1,0,'\sigma\prime_2','fontsize',15)
else
    text((sigma_2-pore_pressure_new)*0.99,0,'\sigma\prime_2','fontsize',15)
end
if sigma_3>0
    text((sigma_3-pore_pressure_new)*1.1,0,'\sigma\prime_3','fontsize',15);
else
    text((sigma_3-pore_pressure_new)*0.99,0,'\sigma\prime_3','fontsize',15);
end
text(Centre1_new(1),tau_1*0.9,'\tau_1','fontsize',15);
text(Centre2_new(1),tau_2*0.9,'\tau_2','fontsize',15);
text(Centre3_new(1),tau_3*0.9,'\tau_3','fontsize',15);
xlabel('Effective Normal Stress, \sigma\prime','fontsize',15);
ylabel('Shear Stress, \tau','fontsize',15)

%Critical injection
sigma_shear_new=c_zero+(coeff_friction_angle*(cirlce1_new(:,1)));
i1=(cirlce1_new(:,2)>=sigma_shear_new);
if sum(i1)>0 %sigma dan envelope adalah vektor jadi harus dikasih sum...
    stopdate=datetime(data_injeksi.date(i),'ConvertFrom','datetime');
    disp(stopdate);
    break
end

truedate=datetime(data_injeksi.date,'ConvertFrom','datetime');
subplot(1,2,2)
hold on
ket=['Injection date: ' str2mat(truedate(i)) ''];
text(4,40,ket)
hold off

%movie
pause(0.1);

end
%% Maximum allowable pore pressure change

critical_angle=90+friction_angle;
critical_normal_stress=((sigma_1+sigma_3)/2)+(((sigma_1-sigma_3)/2)*cosd(critical_angle));
critical_shear_stress=((sigma_1-sigma_3)/2)*sind(critical_angle);
pore_pressure_crit=critical_normal_stress+((c_zero-
critical_shear_stress)/tand(friction_angle));

txta=['Initial pore pressure: ' num2str(pore_pressure) ' MPa'];
text(4,50,txta)
txtb=['Critical pore pressure: ' num2str(pore_pressure_crit) ' MPa'];
text(4,45,txtb)
txtc=['Stop injection at: ' str2mat(stopdate) ''];
text(4,40,txtc)

```